

Condensation of Glutaryl Chloride and Glutaric Anhydride with Di- and Polyhydric Phenols and their Methyl Ethers

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Glutaryl chloride has been condensed with resorcinol, resorcinol dimethyl ether, 4-chlororesorcinol, 4-bromoresorcinol, phloroglucinol, veratrol and chloro-orsinol dimethyl ether in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride producing exclusively 1,5-bis (substituted phenyl)-pentane-1,5 diones. But chlororesorcinol dimethyl ether, bromoresorcinol dimethyl ether and pyrogallol trimethyl ether yielded both diketones and β -keto acids under identical conditions. Orcin and its various ether derivatives provided exclusively the β -keto acids without any trace of the corresponding diketones. However, glutaric anhydride has been found to condense with all the phenols and phenolic ethers mentioned above, yielding exclusively the keto acids.

Although the condensation of glutaryl chloride with benzene leading to the formation of a 1,5 diketone e.g., α , γ -dibenzoylpropane (I. $R=R_1=R_2=R_3=R_4=H$) with a small amount of the keto acid, γ -benzoylbutyric acid (II, $R=R_1=R_2=R_3=R_4=H$) was reported by Auger¹ as early as 1891, it is only very recently that glutaryl chloride has been extensively used in the Friedel-Crafts reaction by Chakravarti and his coworkers². These authors have reported the condensation of glutaryl chloride and glutaric anhydride with monohydric phenols and their methyl ethers.

The present authors have attempted the condensation of di- and polyhydric phenols and their ethers with glutaryl chloride and glutaric anhydride. This glutaroylation of di- and polyhydric phenols and their ethers has served an excellent method for the preparation of aromatic 1,5-diketones and some β -keto acids which are of extreme importance.

In condensing glutaryl chloride with di- and polyhydric phenols, their ethers and their halogenated derivatives, the reaction was found to occur smoothly at $0^\circ-5^\circ$ in nitrobenzene as solvent, the acyl group entering always without any exception to the point which has the maximum directive influence of the hydroxy or the alkoxy groups.

Glutaric anhydride was likewise condensed with the phenols and their ethers but the reaction was possible only at temperatures higher than $50^\circ-60^\circ$ and the condensation has invariably yielded the keto acids which were found identical to those obtained during the condensation of glutaryl chloride.

The structures of the diketone and the keto acid were confirmed by their oxidation to β -resoroylic acid derivatives.

1. Auger, *Annales de Chimie*, (6) 22, 358
2. D. Chakravarti and Nripendra K. Roy, *This Journal*, 1965, 42, 607,

E X P E R I M E N T A L

1,5-bis(2,4-Dimethoxy-5-bromophenyl)pentane-1,5-dione (I, $R=R_2=OMe$; $R_1=R_4=H$; $R_3=Br$). A solution of freshly distilled 4-bromoresorcin dimethyl ether (8.6 g.) in nitrobenzene (25 ml.) was cooled to 0° in a three-necked flask equipped with mechanical stirrer, dropping funnel and a gas outlet tube. Aluminium chloride (12 g.) was added and the resulting mixture was maintained at 0° . Glutaryl chloride (3.6 g.) diluted with nitrobenzene (10 ml.) was added dropwise during a period of 1 hr. The reaction mixture turning deep pink was kept in the refrigerator for 12 hr. After decomposing with ice and conc. HCl, it was distilled in steam to remove nitrobenzene. The crude product which solidified on cooling was treated with $NaHCO_3$ solution when a portion remained insoluble. This was filtered off, washed, crystallised from glacial acetic acid, and had m.p. 193° , yield 4.5 g. (Found: C, 48.17; H, 4.42; $C_{22}H_{24}O_6Br_2$ requires C, 47.87, H, 4.15%).

The dioxime was crystallised from dilute alcohol and had m.p. 205° . (Found: N, 4.86; $C_{21}H_{24}O_6N_2Br_2$ requires N, 5.0%).

Demethylation of the above Diketone.—The diketone (1 g.) was mixed with acetic acid (15 ml.) and HBr (40%) (5 ml.) and the mixture was refluxed for 15 hr. on a sand bath. This was diluted with water and the solid obtained (0.6 g.) was crystallised from alcohol, and had m.p. 214° - 215° . No depression in the mixed m.p. with the diketone obtained from 4-bromo-resorcinol and glutaryl chloride, was noticed.

Oxidation of the above Diketone.—Potassium permanganate (2 g.) in water (75 ml.) was added dropwise under reflux during 4 hr. to the diketone (1 g.) in acetone (50 ml.). The mixture was cleared with SO_2 and extracted with ether. The residue left on evaporation of the extract was dissolved in 5% $NaHCO_3$, filtered and the filtrate on acidification gave a solid which crystallised from dilute acetone and had m.p. 196° . No depression in m.p. on admixture with an authentic sample of 5-bromo β -resorecylic acid dimethyl ether, was observed.

TABLE I
Condensation of Di- and Polyhydric Phenols & their Ethers with Glutaryl Chloride

Phenols and Phenolic Ethers	Products formed	Formulae	Analysis Found	Analysis Reqd.	Derivatives	Remarks
1. Resorcin (in Nitrobenzene)	1,5-bis-[2,4-dihydroxy Phenyl]-pentane 1,5-dione; m.p. 225° (Acetic acid)	$C_{17}H_{16}O_6$ [I, R = R ₂ = OH; R ₁ = R ₃ = H]	C: 64.50% H: 5.12% O: 5.06%	64.55% 5.06%	Oxime, m.p. 238°; (dil. alcohol) [Found: N, 7.82; C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₆ N ₂ requires N, 8.09%]	
2. Resorcin Dimethyl Ether (in Nitrobenzene)	1,5-bis-[2-hydroxy-4-methoxy Phenyl]-pentane 1,5-dione. m.p. 130° (dil. Ethanol)	$C_{19}H_{20}O_6$ [I, R ₂ = OMe; R = OH; R ₁ = R ₃ = R ₄ = H]	C: 65.95 H: 5.64 O: 5.81	66.27 5.81	Oxime, m.p. 190°; (dil. Ethanol) [Found: N, 7.14; C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₂ requires N, 7.48%]	Demethylated Product m.p. 225°; mixed with 1,5-bis [2,4-dihydroxy Phenyl] pentane 1,5-dione; 225°
3. 4-Chloro Resorcin (in Nitrobenzene)	1,5-bis-[2,4-dihydroxy, 5-chloro phenyl]-pentane 1,5-dione. m.p. 223° (Ethanol)	$C_{17}H_{14}O_6Cl_2$ [I, R = R ₂ = OH; R ₁ = R ₃ = H]	C: 55.23 H: 3.99	52.98 3.63	Oxime, m.p. 321° (dil. Ethanol) [Found: N, 6.38; C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₆ Cl ₂ N ₂ requires N, 6.74%]	
4. 4-Chloro Resorcin Dimethyl Ether (in Nitrobenzene)	(a) 1,5-bis-[2,4-dimethoxy-5-chloro phenyl]-pentane 1,5-dione. m.p. 198° (Acetic acid)	$C_{21}H_{20}O_6Cl_2$ [I, R = R ₂ = OMe; R ₃ = Cl; R ₁ = R ₄ = H]	C: 57.08 H: 5.21	57.18 5.20	Oxime, m.p. 208° (Ethanol) [Found: N, 6.26; C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₆ Cl ₂ requires N, 5.94%]	Demethylated Product m.p. 224°; mixed with 1,5-bis-[2,4-dihydroxy-5-chloro phenyl]-pentane 1,5-dione; m.p. 224° (Ethanol)
5. 4-Bromo Resorcin (in Nitrobenzene)	(b) γ-[2,4-dimethoxy-5-Chloro benzoyl] butyric acid. m.p. 160° (Ethanol)	$C_{13}H_{13}O_5Cl$ [I, R = R ₂ = OMe; R ₃ = Cl; R ₁ = R ₄ = H]	C: 54.71 H: 5.85	54.54 5.24	2:4 D.M.P., m.p. 171° (Ethanol) [Found: N, 11.76; C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₅ N ₂ Cl requires N, 12.01%]	
5. 4-Bromo Resorcin (in Nitrobenzene)	1,5-bis-(2,4-dihydroxy-5-Bromo Phenyl)-pentane 1,5-dione. m.p. 215° (Ethanol)	$C_{17}H_{14}O_6Br_2$ [I, R = R ₂ = OH; R ₃ = Br; R ₁ = R ₄ = H]	C: 43.33 H: 2.99	43.04 2.95	2:4 D.M.P., m.p. 262° (Ethanol) [Found: N, 13.28; C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₆ N ₂ Br ₂ requires N, 13.43%]	
6. 4-Bromo Resorcin Dimethyl Ether (in Nitrobenzene)	(a) 1,5-bis-[2,4-dimethoxy-5-Bromo Phenyl]-pentane 1,5-dione. m.p. 193° (Acetic acid)	$C_{21}H_{20}O_6Br_2$ [I, R = R ₂ = OMe; R ₃ = Br; R ₁ = R ₄ = H]	C: 48.17 H: 4.42	47.87 4.15	Oxime, m.p. 205° [Found: N, 4.86; C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₂ Br ₂ requires N, 5.0%]	
6. 4-Bromo Resorcin Dimethyl Ether (in Nitrobenzene)	(b) γ-(2,4-dimethoxy-5-Bromo benzoyl)-butyric. m.p. 134°/135° (Ethanol)	$C_{13}H_{13}O_5Br$ [I, R = R ₂ = OMe; R ₃ = Br; R ₁ = R ₄ = H]	C: 47.30 H: 4.28	47.12 4.53	2:4 D.M.P., m.p. 181° (Ethanol) [Found: N, 11.32; C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₅ N ₂ Br requires N, 10.95%]	Oxidation Product, m.p. 196°; mixed with 3-Bromo β-resorcylic acid Dimethyl Ether, m.p. 196° (water)
7. Veratrole (in Tetrachloro Ethane)	1,5-bis-[3,4-dimethoxy Phenyl]-pentane 1,5-dione; m.p. 124° (Ethanol)	$C_{21}H_{24}O_6$ [I, R ₂ = R ₃ = OMe; R = R ₁ = R ₄ = H]	C: 68.15 H: 6.91	67.74 6.45	Oxime, m.p. 150° (dil. Ethanol) [Found: N, 15.56; C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₂ requires N, 15.31%]	

TABLE I (contd.)

Phenols and Phenolic Ethers	Products formed	Formulae	Analysis	Derivatives	Remarks
			Found	Reqd.	
8. Orcinol (in Nitrobenzene)	γ -(2,4-dihydroxy-6-methylbenzoyl)-butyric acid; m.p. 218° (dil. methanol)	$C_{12}H_{14}O_5$ [I], R = R ₂ = OH; R ₃ = Me; R ₁ = R ₃ = H]	C: 60.74 H: 6.08	60.50 5.89	Oxime, m.p. 140° [Found: N, 5.91; C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₅ N requires N, 5.53%]
9. Orcinol Dimethyl Ether (in Nitrobenzene)	γ -(2,4-dimethoxy-6-methylbenzoyl)-butyric acid. m.p. 130° (dil. methanol)	$C_{14}H_{18}O_5$ [I], R = R ₂ = OMe; R ₃ = Me; R ₁ = R ₃ = H]	C: 62.92 H: 7.16	63.15 6.76	Demethylated Product m.p. 216°; mixed with γ -(2,4-dihydroxy-6- methylbenzoyl)buty- ric acid, m.p. 218° (dil. methanol)
10. 4-Chloro Orcinol (in Nitrobenzene)	γ -(2,4-dihydroxy-5-chloro-6-methylbenzoyl)-butyric acid. m.p. 172° (dil. methanol)	$C_{12}H_{13}O_5Cl$ [I], R = R ₂ = OH; R ₃ = Cl, R ₁ = H; R ₄ = Me]	C: 51.22 H: 4.67	50.56 4.24	2,4 D.N.P.; m.p. 191° [Found: N, 13.15; C, 52.4; O ₈ N ₂ Cl requires N, 12.78%]
11. 4-Chloro Orcinol Dimethyl Ether	1,5-bis-[2,4-dimethoxy-5-chloro-6-methylphenyl]-pentane 1,5-dione, m.p. 145° (Ethanol)	$C_{24}H_{26}O_8Cl$ [I], R = R ₂ = OMe; R ₃ = Cl; R ₄ = Me; R ₁ = H]	C: 64.12 H: 5.85	63.74 6.04	2,4 D.N.P.; m.p. 176° (dil. Ethanol) [Found: N, 14.36; C ₂₅ H ₂₈ O ₁₀ ClN ₂ requires N, 14.12%]
12. 4-Bromo Orcinol (in Nitrobenzene)	γ -(2,4-dihydroxy-5-bromo-6-methylbenzoyl)-butyric acid. m.p. 176° (dil. methanol)	$C_{12}H_{13}O_5Br$ [I], R = R ₂ = OH; R ₃ = Br; R ₄ = Me; R ₁ = H]	C: 43.32 H: 3.98	43.56 3.63	2,4 D.N.P. m.p. 179° (Ethanol) [Found: N, 11.35; C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₈ Br N ₂ requires N, 11.59%]
13. 4-Bromo Orcinol Dimethyl Ether	γ -(2,4-dimethoxy-5-bromo-6-methylbenzoyl)-butyric acid.	$C_{14}H_{17}O_5Br$ [I], R = R ₂ = OMe; R ₃ = Br; R ₄ = Me; R ₁ = H]	C: 48.32 H: 5.12	48.69 4.92	Demethylated Product, m.p. 176°; mixed with γ -(2,4-dihydroxy -6-methylbenzoyl)buty- ric acid, m.p. 176° (dil. methanol)
14. Phloroglucinol (in Nitrobenzene & Tetra-chloroethane)	1,5-bis-[2,4,6-trihydroxyphenyl]-pentane-1,5-dione (Acetic acid)	$C_{17}H_{10}O_8$ [I], R = R ₂ = R ₃ = OH; R ₁ = R ₃ = H]	C: 60.02 H: 3.25	59.64 2.92	2,4 D. N. P.; m.p. 278° (Ethanol) [Found: N, 16.46; C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₁₄ N ₂ requires N, 15.95%]
15. Pyrogallol Trimethyl Ether (in Nitrobenzene)	(a) 1,5-bis-[2-hydroxy-3,4-dimethoxyphenyl]-pentane-1,5-dione, m.p. 125° (acetic acid)	$C_{21}H_{24}O_8$ [I, R = OH; R ₁ = R ₂ = OMe; R ₃ = R ₄ = H]	C: 61.99 H: 5.88	62.37 5.94	Oxime, m.p. 167.8° (dil. Ethanol) [Found: N, 6.76; C ₂₁ H ₂₆ O ₈ N ₂ requires N, 6.45%]
	(b) γ -(2,3,4-trimethoxybenzoyl)-butyric acid; m.p. 72-3° (dil. methanol)	$C_{14}H_{16}O_6$ [I], R = R ₁ = R ₂ = OMe; R ₃ = R ₄ = H]	C: 59.35 H: 6.10	59.57 6.38	2,4 D.N.P.; m.p. 155° (Ethanol) [Found: N, 12.41; C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₈ N ₂ requires N, 12.12%]

TABLE II
Condensation of Di- and Polyhydric Phenols & their Ethers with Glutaric Anhydride

Phenol and Phenolic Ether	Products formed	Formula	Analysis Found	Analysis Req'd.	Derivatives	Remarks
1. 4-Chloro Resorcinol (in Nitrobenzene)	γ -(2,4-dihydroxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-butyric acid; m.p. 140° (dil. methanol)	$C_{11}H_{11}O_5Cl$ [II, R= R_4 =OH; R ₅ =Cl; R ₁ =R ₂ =H]	C: 51.60% H: 4.42%	51.16% 4.26%	2,4-D.N.P. m.p. 171° (Ethanol). [Found: N, 13.12; C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₈ N ₄ Cl requires N, 12.78%]	
2. 4-Bromo Resorcinol (in Nitrobenzene)	γ -(2,4-dihydroxy-5-bromobenzoyl)-butyric acid; m.p. 123° (dil. ethanol)	$C_{11}H_{11}O_5Br$ [II, R= R_4 =OH, R ₅ =Br; R ₁ =R ₂ =H]	C: 59.40 H: 5.20	59.19 4.93	2,4-D.N.P.; m.p. 225° (Ethanol); [Found: N, 11.09; C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₈ Br N ₄ requires N, 11.59%]	
3. 4-Chloro Resorcinol Dimethyl Ether (in Nitrobenzene)	γ -(2,4-dimethoxy-5-chlorobenzoyl)-butyric acid; m.p. 160°-61° (ethanol)	$C_{13}H_{15}O_5Cl$ [II, R= R_4 =OMe; R ₅ =Cl; R ₁ =R ₂ =H]	C: 54.11 H: 5.85	54.54 5.24	2,4-D.N.P.; m.p. 171° (Ethanol). [Found: N, 11.76; C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₈ N ₄ Cl requires N, 12.01%]	
4. 4-Bromo Resorcinol Dimethyl Ether (in Nitrobenzene)	γ -(2,4-dimethoxy-5-bromobenzoyl)-butyric acid; m.p. 134° (dil. methanol)	$C_{13}H_{15}O_5Br$ [II, R= R_4 =OMe; R ₅ =Br; R ₁ =R ₂ =H]	C: 47.39 H: 4.28	47.12 4.53	2,4-D.N.P.; m.p. 181° (Ethanol) [Found: N, 11.32; C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₈ N ₄ Br requires N, 10.93%]	Oxidation Product; m.p. 196°; mixed with 5-bromo β -resorcylic acid dimethyl ether, m.p. 196° (water)
5. Orcinol (in Nitrobenzene)	γ -(2,4-dihydroxy-6-methylbenzoyl)-butyric acid; m.p. 218° (water)	$C_{12}H_{14}O_5$ [R= R_4 =OH; R ₅ =Me; R ₁ =R ₂ =H]	C: 60.74 H: 6.08	60.50 5.89	Oxime, m.p. 140° (dil ethanol) [Found: N, 5.91; C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ requires N, 5.53%]	
6. Orcinol Dimethyl Ether (in Nitrobenzene)	γ -(2,4-dimethoxy-6-methylbenzoyl)-butyric acid	$C_{14}H_{18}O_5$ [II, R= R_4 =OMe; R ₅ =Me; R ₁ =R ₂ =H]	C: 62.92 H: 7.16	63.15 6.76	2,4-D.N.P.; m.p. 155° (ethanol) [Found: N, 13.00; C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₈ N ₄ requires N, 12.55%]	Demethylated Product m.p. 218°; mixed with γ -(2,4-dihydroxy-6-methylbenzoyl)-butyric acid, m.p. 218°;
7. 4-Chloro-orcinol (in Nitrobenzene)	γ -(2,4-dihydroxy-5-chloro-6-methylbenzoyl)-butyric acid; m.p. 172° (dil. methanol)	$C_{12}H_{14}O_5Cl$ [II, R= R_4 =OH; R ₅ =Me; R ₁ =R ₂ =H]	C: 51.22 H: 4.67	50.96 4.24	2,4-D.N.P.; m.p. 191° (ethanol) [Found: N, 13.15; C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₈ N ₄ Cl requires N, 12.78%]	butyric acid, m.p. 218°;
8. 4-Bromo Orcinol (in Nitrobenzene)	γ -(2,4-dihydroxy-5-bromo-6-methylbenzoyl)-butyric acid; m.p. 176° (dil. methanol)	$C_{12}H_{14}O_5Br$ [II, R= R_4 =OH; R ₅ =Br; R ₁ =R ₂ =H]	C: 43.52 H: 3.98	43.56 3.63	2,4-D.N.P.; m.p. 179° (ethanol) [Found: N, 11.55; C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₈ Br N ₄ requires N, 11.59%]	Demethylated Product, m.p. 176°; mixed with γ -(2,4-dihydroxy-5-bromo-6-methylbenzoyl)-butyric acid; m.p. 176° (dil. methanol)
9. 4-Bromo Orcinol Dimethyl Ether (in Nitrobenzene)	γ -(2,4-dimethoxy-5-bromo-6-methylbenzoyl)-butyric acid; m.p. 117° (dil methanol)	$C_{14}H_{18}O_5Br$ [II, R= R_4 =OMe; R ₅ =Br; R ₁ =R ₂ =H]	C: 48.52 H: 4.12	48.69 4.92		

Treatment of the NaHCO₃-soluble Portion. (II, R=R₂=OMe; R₁=R₃=H; R₄=Br.)—The aqueous alkaline solution was acidified with HCl when γ -(2,4-dimethoxy-5-bromobenzoyl)-butyric acid separated out. It was crystallised from alcohol; m.p. 134°–135°, yield 2 g. (Found: C, 47.39; H, 4.28; C₁₃H₁₃O₅Br requires C, 47.12; H, 4.53%).

The 2 : 4 *D.N.P.* was crystallised from alcohol, and had m.p. 181°. (Found: N, 11.32; C₁₉H₁₉O₅N₄Br requires N, 10.95%).

Oxidation of the above Keto-acid.—The keto acid (1 g.) dissolved in 50 ml. 5% NaOH solution was slowly oxidised by the addition of 25 ml. 2% NaOBr solution. The solution was acidified and extracted with ether. After evaporation of ether 5-bromo β -oxo-cyclic acid dimethyl ether was obtained, crystallised from water, and had m.p. 196°. No depression in m.p. on admixture with an authentic sample, was observed.

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